

A palaeogravity calculation for the ancient land scorpion *Pulmonoscorpius kirktonensis*

Stephen W. Hurrell

email: papers@dinox.org

First Published: 19th April 2022

Cite: Hurrell, S.W. (2022). A palaeogravity calculation for the ancient land scorpion *Pulmonoscorpius kirktonensis*. <http://dinox.org/hurrell2022a>

Abstract

One fundamental technique to quantify palaeogravity is to compare dynamically similar extinct and extant animals. This technique is applied to the ancient land scorpion *Pulmonoscorpius kirktonensis*. The results indicate a palaeogravity of about 0.33g existed 330 million years ago.

Key words: Palaeogravity, *Pulmonoscorpius kirktonensis*.

Introduction to fossil land scorpions

Scorpions are a very successful ancient arthropod group. There are over 2,400 extant species and their basic body plan has remained unchanged for hundreds of millions of years. Howard *et al* (2019) details a reasonably continuous fossil record stretching back to the Silurian.

Land scorpions have one of the most complete fossil records. Over one hundred fossil species are currently recognised, while the majority of these are Palaeozoic in age due to the excellent conditions available for preservation. There has been ongoing debate about whether scorpions were fully terrestrial or aquatic but the identification of “book lungs” is often taken as confirmation that they were fully terrestrial.

The East Kirkton Limestone quarry, near Edinburgh in Scotland, is a remarkable example of hot spring activity within a small volcanic lake

forming some exquisitely detailed fossils from around 330 million years ago. Layers of calcium carbonate were precipitated as a result of the hot spring activity, forming a thinly bedded limestone. This preserved the plants and animals in fine detail.

Fossil scorpions with an excellent state of preservation have been found at East Kirkton. According to Clack (2012) these fossils have allowed much more detailed information to be gained from these fossils than any other previous site, and it has meant that these scorpions, and others, can be interpreted more accurately. There have been a large number of fossils recovered almost in their original three-dimensional state. Details of the claws, eyes and bristles can be seen. This is highly unusual since scorpion fossils are often only preserved as compressed and blackened stains in the rock.

Most of the specimens belong to the single species, *Pulmonoscorpius kirktonensis*, and have been described in detail by Jeram (1994). Because it has been

Figure 1. The ancient land scorpion *Pulmonoscorpium kirktonensis* is remarkably similar to a modern-day scorpion. It had “book lungs”, enabling it to follow a terrestrial mode of life very similar to its modern day relatives. It was much larger than its modern-day relatives, reaching up to 70 cm in length. This figure of a nearly complete specimen was reproduced in Jeram (1994) as figure 4. The image is available for download from GB3D Type Fossils (see reference section).

possible to identify an air breathing mechanism called a book lung, it is highly likely that this scorpion was a terrestrial animal. One of the most complete fossils recovered (fig. 1) shows an animal that has changed little over hundreds of millions of years, except in size. Most of the specimens recovered were juveniles, but the largest incomplete fossil has been estimated to have been 70 cm long. With its close similarity to a modern land scorpion it is easy to imagine that it followed a very similar mode of life to a modern-day scorpion. With the characteristic scorpion sting at the end of its tail this must have been a fearsome predator.

A calculation of palaeogravity

Theoretically, the largest of the extant land scorpions will have reached their maximum viable size limit due to the scale effect. The extinct land scorpions would have reached a larger viable size limit if palaeogravity was less at that time. Assuming that the largest *Pulmonoscorpium kirktonensis* recorded in the fossil record moved in a dynamically similar way to the largest of the extant scorpions we can calculate palaeogravity from:

$$g = S_n / S_x$$

where S_n is the relative size of the extant giant scorpion, and S_x is the relative size of *Pulmonoscorpium kirktonensis*. The derivation of this formula is discussed in detail in Hurrell (2011).

Assuming that the *Pulmonoscorpium kirktonensis* reached its maximum size limit in a reduced gravity, it can be compared with the largest land scorpion in a 1g environment. There are over 2,400 species of extant scorpions and various species have approached the maximum viable size in our current gravity. *Hadogenes troglodytes*, commonly known as the flat rock scorpion, had the longest recorded length of any scorpion until a few years ago. Punzo (2000) described one with a length of 20 cm. However, Rubio (2000) described a *Heterometrus swammerdami*, commonly called the giant forest scorpion, which was 23 cm in length. Therefore, the length of the largest extant giant scorpion is taken as 23 cm while the length of the largest extinct scorpion is taken as 70 cm.

Punzo (2000). "Scorpions (Scorpiones)". Desert arthropods: life history variations. Springer. pp. 128–138. ISBN 978-3-540-66041-5.

Rubio (2000). "Commonly Available Scorpions". Scorpions: Everything About Purchase, Care, Feeding, and Housing. Barron's. pp. 26–27. ISBN 978-0-7641-1224-9.

Thus:

$$g \approx 23 / 70 = 0.33g$$

This estimate of palaeogravity compares an ancient land scorpion to dynamically similar extant land scorpions and so it is probably more accurate than previous palaeogravity estimates for scorpions, as given in Hurrell (2012). It would be better to use the new estimate of about 0.33g at 330 million years ago instead of the older estimate.

References

Clack, J. A. (2012). Gaining ground: the origin and evolution of tetrapods. Indiana University Press.

GB3D Type Fossils. Fossil specimen : NMS NMS G.1987.7.136. <http://www.3d-fossils.ac.uk/fossilType.cfm?typSampleId=25001235>

Hurrell, S. W. (2011). Dinosaurs and the Expanding Earth. Oneoff Publishing.com

Hurrell, S. (2012). Ancient Life's Gravity and its Implications for the Expanding Earth. In The Earth Expansion Evidence – A Challenge for Geology, Geophysics and Astronomy - Selected Contributions to the Interdisciplinary Workshop of the 37th International School of Geophysics. Aracne Editrice, Roma.

Jeram, A. J. (1994). Scorpions from the Viséan of East Kirkton, West Lothian, Scotland, with a revision of the infraorder Mesoscorpionina. Earth and Environmental Science Transactions of The Royal Society of Edinburgh, 84(3-4), 283-299.